

Analysis of Leadership Styles among Headmasters of Secondary Schools

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Abstract

Leadership is defined typically by qualities, behaviours and traits which persist in a leader. Leadership study spans across decades, theoretical beliefs and different cultures. A summarized form which is being understood by the researchers is important for future research based on leadership. Comprehensive review about leadership theories, different categories have been identified in previous studies which captured the importance of leadership as a study in twentieth century. First category of leadership deals with attributes of the great leaders. Leadership has been explained by internal qualities which are in a person. Thought about traits which differentiated the leaders from their followers can be identified and successful leaders can be identified quickly and are put into leadership positions. This study is mainly focused on evaluating the features of leadership styles, understand the different types of leadership styles and investigate differences among headmasters working in secondary schools in Bengaluru Rural, Bengaluru Urban and Chikkaballapur district of Karnataka state with respect to different leadership styles. The hypothesis have been tested through ANOVA.

Keywords: Leadership Style, ANOVA, Headmasters, Secondary School.

1. Introduction

During the past few years, leadership is being studied in an extensive manner based on theoretical foundations and various contexts. In certain cases, leadership is considered to be a process, but in certain research and theories based on leadership, it is considered as an important aspect for gaining an understanding. Leadership is defined typically by qualities, behaviours and traits which persist in a leader. Leadership study spans across decades, theoretical beliefs and different cultures. A summarized form which is being understood by the researchers is important for future research based on leadership.

Comprehensive review about leadership theories, different categories have been identified in previous studies which captured the importance of leadership as a study in twentieth century. First category of leadership deals with attributes of the great leaders. Leadership has been explained by internal qualities which are in a person. Thought about traits which differentiated the leaders from their followers can be identified and successful leaders can be identified quickly and are put into leadership positions. Physical, mental and personality characteristics have been examined. This current research has been based on idea with which the leaders were born and not made and key towards success has been simply identified those people those who were born as great leaders. Though there have not been much research which identified traits that were consistently associated with the great leadership. The leadership is said to be a line of thought wherein the environmental and situational factors play a very important role in effectiveness level.

The Leaders who are leading the organization and the leadership skills which they have play a very important role and adds towards growth of organization. Leadership can be referred to process of

influencing people's behaviour in a way which strives manner that they strive enthusiastically and willingly towards achievement of various group objectives.

It is important for the leader to have ability related to maintenance of a good impersonal relation with subordinates or followers and motivate them to achieve organizational objectives.

2. Features of Leadership

There are different features of leadership and some of them have been mentioned below:

- **Influence behaviour of the others:** Leadership can be said to be an ability which helps in influencing behaviour of the other employees in organization for achieving common goal or purpose so that they could co-operate with the other in fulfilling the same.
- **Inter-personal process:** Leadership is said to be interpersonal process which exists between followers and leaders. Relationship between followers and leaders decide how effectively and efficiently the target of organization could be met.
- **Attainment of organizational goals:** Leadership has a purpose of guiding people working in the organization to work toward attaining organizational goals which are common to the organization. Leader makes an attempt to bring people together and make them put efforts towards achievement of common goals.
- **Continuous process:** Leadership is said to be continuous process. Leader needs to guide their employees each time and also should monitor them for making sure that the efforts are moving towards same direction and there needs to be a check that the people are not getting deviated from the goals of the organization.
- **Group process:** Leadership is group process which involves more than two people together to interact with each other. It is not possible for a leader to lead without having followers.
- **Dependent on situation:** Leadership is situation bound and it depends upon handling of the current situation. Hence, it can be said that there is no such single leadership style which could be said to be the best.

3. Common leadership styles

There are many leadership styles and a few of them have been discussed below:

1. Coach

Coaching leader will be one who could recognize quickly the strengths, motivations and weaknesses of their team members and help them in improving themselves. Leader when acts as a coach, help their team members in setting smart goals and they provide feedbacks regularly to the team members.

2. Visionary

Visionary leaders are having powerful ability for driving progress in the period of change through inspiring their employees and also earning trust for innovative ideas. Leaders expect their followers to have a clear vision in their life and work towards the same in the longer run.

3. Servant

The servant leaders are the ones who work having people first set of mind and they believe that when the team members feel professionally and personally fulfilled, they work more effectively and also produce a great work on regular basis. These type of leaders emphasize more on collaboration and employee satisfaction, hence they are able to achieve a higher respect from the followers.

4. Autocratic

A person who is a leader with an authoritarian is more focused on efficiency and results. They generally make decisions on their own or with the help of a trusted or small group and they expect the employees to work exactly as he or she expects them to do. Such leaders could work well as the military commanders. This type of leadership style could be helpful in different organizations having strict rules and regulations or heavily compliant.

5. Laissez-faire or hands-off

This kind of leadership is opposite of autocratic leadership and focuses more on delegation of many tasks for their team members and also provide a very little or even sometimes no such supervision. In

this type of leadership, the leader does not spend much of their time with the employees and hence they are able to dedicate more time for the other projects.

6. Democratic

This type of leadership style is said to be a combination of laissez-faire and autocratic type of leadership. Democratic leader generally ask their employees to provide feedback from their team, before he or she could make a final decision. The employees feel that their leader would hear their voice and the contribution by them also matters a lot. In a democratic leadership, the style often is known for higher workplace satisfaction and employee engagement.

7. Pacesetter

It is a leadership style which is said to be quite effective and drives good results. Such leaders mainly focus on performance. They generally set higher standards and also hold team members accountable in hitting their goals. This type of leadership style would be helpful and motivational in the environment which was fast paced environment.

8. Transformational

This type of leadership is said to be similar like coach style, wherein there is a focus on employee motivation, goal setting and clear communication. This leadership style focuses on the organizations goals as a whole and do not focus on goals of the employees individually. This kind of leader is driven by commitment towards organization's objectives.

9. Transactional

A transactional leader is someone who is laser-focused on performance similar to a pacesetter. Under this leadership style, the manager establishes predetermined incentives usually in the form of monetary reward for success and disciplinary action for failure. Unlike the pacesetter leadership style, transactional leaders are also focused on mentorship, instruction and training to achieve goals and enjoy the rewards.

While this type of leader is great for organisations or teams tasked with hitting specific goals such as sales and revenue, it's not the best leadership style for driving creativity.

10. Bureaucratic

Bureaucratic leaders are similar to autocratic leaders in that they expect their team members to follow the rules and procedures precisely as written.

The bureaucratic leadership style focuses on fixed duties within a hierarchy where each employee has a set list of responsibilities and there is little need for collaboration and creativity. This leadership style is most effective in highly regulated industries or departments such as finance, healthcare or government.

Remember, most leaders borrow from a variety of styles to achieve various goals at different times in their career. While you may have excelled in a role using one type of leadership, another position may require a different set of habits to ensure your team is operating most effectively.

By understanding each of these leadership types, and the outcomes they're designed to achieve, you can select the right leadership style for your current situation.

The leadership styles can either be classified on the basis of behavioral approach or situational approach. These approaches are comprised of several theories and models which are explained below

4. Review of Literature

Hui, Lim Siew et. al., (2020) have mentioned in the study based on Influence of the Instructional Leadership on the Learning Organization. This study is based on the performance of primary schools. The area of study is Malaysia. Transforming schools into learning organization and they require significant mindset, cultural shift as well as commitment which is school-wide to evaluation and self-reflection. It is very important for the headmasters to increase their skills and competencies while practicing of the instructional leadership while at school. A sample of 286 teachers have been considered from primary schools in northern zone.

Abu Nasra, Muhammed (2020) have conducted this study to understand the Leadership Style as well as Teacher Performance. This study has the main purpose for development of model wherein leadership style indirectly and directly affects the teacher's performance. Research hypothesis in the

study holds leadership style as transactional or transformational having indirect or direct effect on the teacher's performance. Additionally, results revealed that effect of the transformational principal leadership style based on OCB which is expressed only by the indirect effect.

Özgenel, Mustafa et.al., (2020) conducted this study based on the effect which School's Principal Leadership Style on Leadership Practice. This kind of practices play very crucial role in teacher's performance and this would also impact the effectiveness of school. Focal point of Principal presents research which is investigates leadership style level which is predictive in nature towards leadership practice is based on the teacher's perceptions.

Rehman, Ahsan-Ur et.al., (2019) has conducted this study based on perception of the head of school related to leadership style. This particular study explored the school head perception regarding the leadership style. This study adopted a research design which is qualitative in nature. Sample in this study consisted 10 males and 10 females head teachers from Peshawar. Primary data has been collected through semi-structured interview. The findings have revealed that the school heads have adopted different leadership styles.

Keattholetswe, Lesika et.al., (2019) have conducted this study based on the perception of players, team performance and coaching efficacy in the Premier League Soccer. Coaching competency research demonstrated role of coaching behaviors and coaching efficacy on the athlete's outcomes. Athlete's perception of relationships and they have affected the performance which has been lesser understood. The findings of the study have indicated that the coaches' self-rating on the technique efficacy have predicted players' perception of coaches' have used of six leadership style.

5. Objectives

- To evaluate the features of leadership styles
- To investigate differences among headmasters working in secondary schools in Bengaluru Rural, Bengaluru Urban and Chikkaballapur district of Karnataka state with respect to different leadership styles

6. Hypothesis

- H₀₁ - There is no significance difference in leadership styles and its dimensions among secondary school headmasters working in Bengaluru Rural, Bengaluru Urban and Chikkaballapur district of Karnataka state.
H₁₁ - There is a significance difference in leadership styles and its dimensions among secondary school headmasters working in Bengaluru Rural, Bengaluru Urban and Chikkaballapur district of Karnataka state.
- H₀₂ - There is no significance difference in Transformational Leadership among secondary school headmasters working in Bengaluru Rural, Bengaluru Urban and Chikkaballapur district of Karnataka state.
H₁₂ - There is a significance difference in Transformational Leadership among secondary school headmasters working in Bengaluru Rural, Bengaluru Urban and Chikkaballapur district of Karnataka state.
- H₀₃ - There is no significance difference in Transactional Leadership among secondary school headmasters working in Bengaluru Rural, Bengaluru Urban and Chikkaballapur district of Karnataka state.
H₁₃ - There is a significance difference in Transactional Leadership among secondary school headmasters working in Bengaluru Rural, Bengaluru Urban and Chikkaballapur district of Karnataka state.
- H₀₄ - There is no significance difference in Laissez-faire Leadership among secondary school headmasters working in Bengaluru Rural, Bengaluru Urban and Chikkaballapur district of Karnataka state.

H₁₄ - There is a significance difference in Laissez-faire Leadership among secondary school headmasters working in Bengaluru Rural, Bengaluru Urban and Chikkaballapur district of Karnataka state.

7. Research Methodology

This study is based on 40 sample of head masters from Rural areas in Bengaluru, 40 from Bengaluru Urban and 40 from Chikkaballapur district. A sample of total 120 head masters have been a part of the study. Data has been collected through a structured questionnaire. ANOVA has been applied for testing the hypothesis. The hypothesis are based on finding out the difference in leadership styles and its dimensions among secondary school headmasters working in Bengaluru Rural, Bengaluru Urban and Chikkaballapur district of Karnataka state.

8. Data Analysis

- H₀₁ - There is no significance difference in leadership styles and its dimensions among secondary school headmasters working in Bengaluru Rural, Bengaluru Urban and Chikkaballapur district of Karnataka state.

H₁₁ - There is a significance difference in leadership styles and its dimensions among secondary school headmasters working in Bengaluru Rural, Bengaluru Urban and Chikkaballapur district of Karnataka state.

Table-1: ANOVA - Leadership styles and its dimensions among secondary school headmasters

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	S/NS
Between Groups	10376.217	2	5188.108	28.813	.000	S
Within Groups	21067.375	117	180.063			
Total	31443.592	119				

Based on the table above, the value of p as indicated below the column titled Sig. is 0.000 and the value of F is 28.813. ANOVA has been applied through SPSS and the table above has been obtained. P value obtained is based on the mean score of leadership styles and their dimensions of headmasters of secondary schools who are working in rural and urban area of Bengaluru and Chikkaballapur district belonging to Karnataka state. Since the value of p as mentioned in table above is less than 0.05 (based on 5% significant level), based on the value being less than 0.05, the null hypothesis has been rejected and the alternate hypothesis has been accepted. The alternate hypothesis represents difference between the leadership styles and their dimensions among the headmasters in secondary school working in rural and urban areas of Bengaluru and Chikkaballapur district of the Karnataka state.

Table-2: Comparison of differences in leadership styles and its dimensions among secondary school headmasters

Districts	N	Mean	SD	Districts	
				Bengaluru Urban	Chikkaballapur
Bengaluru Rural	40	96.9000	16.95514	.000 (p <.05)	.096 (p > .05)
Bengaluru Urban	40	119.0000	9.79534		.000 (p <.05)
Chikkaballapur	40	103.1750	12.52052		

The above table indicates the number of head masters who have been a part of this study, mean and standard deviation. There are 40 sample of head masters from Rural areas in Bengaluru, 40 from Bengaluru Urban and 40 from Chikkaballapur. The mean of the response given by the respondents belonging to Bengaluru Rural is 96.9 and standard deviation is 16.95514. The mean of the response given by the respondents belonging to Bengaluru Urban is 119 and standard deviation is 9.79534. The

mean of the response given by the respondents belonging to Chikkaballapur is 103.175 and standard deviation is 12.52052 for leadership styles and its dimensions of secondary school headmasters. P value is obtained through multiple comparison and this indicates the following:

- Based on ANOVA, there is a significant difference in the leadership styles and their dimensions of the secondary school headmasters who are working in Rural and Urban districts of Bengaluru since the value of p is less than 0.05.
- There is no significant difference in the leadership styles and their dimensions of the secondary school headmasters who are working in Bengaluru Rural and Chikkaballapur district since the value of p is above 0.05.
- There is a significant difference in the leadership styles and their dimensions of the secondary school headmasters who are working in Bengaluru Urban and Chikkaballapur district since the value of p is less than 0.05.

Hence, this study has indicated that the headmasters who are working in Urban district in Bengaluru have shown greater leadership style and their dimensions are compared to Chikkaballapur and Bengaluru Rural district. Overall, this study revealed that headmasters who are working in Urban district in Bengaluru was found to be a higher leadership style as compared to Chikaballapur district and Bengaluru Rural. Difference exists in leadership style and dimension of Bengaluru Urban, Bengaluru Rural district and Chikaballapura district and there is no such difference as mentioned by the teachers working in Chikaballapura district Bengaluru Rural district.

Graph-1: Comparison of leadership styles and its dimensions among secondary school headmasters

- **H₀₂ - There is no significance difference in Transformational Leadership among secondary school headmasters working in Bengaluru Rural, Bengaluru Urban and Chikkaballapur district of Karnataka state.**

H₁₂ - There is a significance difference in Transformational Leadership among secondary school headmasters working in Bengaluru Rural, Bengaluru Urban and Chikkaballapur district of Karnataka state.

Table-3: ANOVA - Transformational Leadership among secondary school headmasters

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	S/NS
Between Groups	3167.717	2	1583.858	18.572	.000	S
Within Groups	9977.750	117	85.280			
Total	13145.467	119				

Based on the table above, the value of p as indicated below the column titled Sig. is 0.000 and the value of F is 18.572. ANOVA has been applied through SPSS and the table above has been obtained. P

value obtained is based on the mean score of Transformational Leadership among secondary school headmasters who are working in rural and urban area of Bengaluru and Chikkaballapur district belonging to Karnataka state. Since the value of p as mentioned in table above is less than 0.05 (based on 5% significant level), based on the value being less than 0.05, the null hypothesis has been rejected and the alternate hypothesis has been accepted. The alternate hypothesis represents difference between Transformational Leadership among secondary school headmasters in rural and urban areas of Bengaluru and Chikkaballapur district of the Karnataka state.

Table-4 : Comparison of differences in Transformational Leadership among secondary school headmasters working in Bengaluru Rural, Bengaluru Urban and Chikkaballapur district of Karnataka state

Districts	N	Mean	SD	Districts	
				Bengaluru Urban	Chikkaballapur
Bengaluru Rural	40	54.6250	10.88327	.000 (p < .05)	.015 (p < .05)
Bengaluru Urban	40	67.2000	7.20114		.004 (p < .05)
Chikkaballapur	40	60.4750	9.24867		

The above table indicates the number of head masters who have been a part of this study, mean and standard deviation. There are 40 sample of head masters from Rural areas in Bengaluru, 40 from Bengaluru Urban and 40 from Chikkaballapur. The mean of the response given by the respondents belonging to Bengaluru Rural is 54.625 and standard deviation is 10.88327. The mean of the response given by the respondents belonging to Bengaluru Urban is 67.2 and standard deviation is 7.20114. The mean of the response given by the respondents belonging to Chikkaballapur is 60.475 and standard deviation is 9.24867 for Transformational Leadership among secondary school headmasters working. P value is obtained through multiple comparison and this indicates the following:

- Based on ANOVA, there is a significant difference in the Transformational Leadership of the secondary school headmasters who are working in Rural and Urban districts of Bengaluru Rural since the value of p is less than 0.05.
- There is a significant difference in the Transformational Leadership of the secondary school headmasters who are working in Bengaluru Rural and Chikkaballapur district since the value of p is less than 0.05.
- There is a significant difference in the Transformational Leadership of the secondary school headmasters who are working in Bengaluru Urban and Chikkaballapur district since the value of p is less than 0.05.

Hence, this study has indicated that the headmasters who are working in Urban district in Bengaluru have shown greater Transformational leadership are compared to Chikkaballapur and Bengaluru Rural district. Overall, this study revealed that headmasters who are working in Urban district in Bengaluru was found to be a higher Transformational leadership as compared to Chikaballapur district and Bengaluru Rural. Difference exists in Transformational leadership of Bengaluru Urban, Bengaluru Rural district and Chikaballapura district and there is a difference as mentioned by the teachers working in Chikaballapura district and Bengaluru Rural district.

Graph-2: Comparison of Transformational Leadership dimensions among secondary school headmasters

- **H₀₃ - There is no significance difference in Transactional Leadership among secondary school headmasters working in Bengaluru Rural, Bengaluru Urban and Chikkaballapur district of Karnataka state.**
H₁₃ - There is a significance difference in Transactional Leadership among secondary school headmasters working in Bengaluru Rural, Bengaluru Urban and Chikkaballapur district of Karnataka state.

Table-5: ANOVA - Transactional Leadership among secondary school headmasters

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	S/NS
Between Groups	1285.550	2	642.775	25.740	.000	S
Within Groups	2921.750	117	24.972			
Total	4207.300	119				

Based on the table above, the value of p as indicated below the column titled Sig. is 0.000 and the value of F is 25.740. ANOVA has been applied through SPSS and the table above has been obtained. P value obtained is based on the mean score of Transactional Leadership among secondary school headmasters who are working in rural and urban area of Bengaluru and Chikkaballapur district belonging to Karnataka state. Since the value of p as mentioned in table above is less than 0.05 (based on 5% significant level), based on the value being less than 0.05, the null hypothesis has been rejected and the alternate hypothesis has been accepted. The alternate hypothesis represents difference between Transactional Leadership among secondary school headmasters in rural and urban areas of Bengaluru and Chikkaballapur district of the Karnataka state.

Table-6 : Comparison of differences in Transactional Leadership among secondary school headmasters

Districts	N	Mean	SD	Districts	
				Bengaluru Urban	Chikkaballapur
Bengaluru Rural	40	31.6750	6.28546	.000 (p <.05)	.954 (p > .05)
Bengaluru Urban	40	38.7750	3.58406		.000 (p <.05)

Chikkaballapur	40	32.0000	4.75017		
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The above table indicates the number of head masters who have been a part of this study, mean and standard deviation. There are 40 sample of head masters from Rural areas in Bengaluru, 40 from Bengaluru Urban and 40 from Chikkaballapur. The mean of the response given by the respondents belonging to Bengaluru Rural is 31.675 and standard deviation is 6.28546. The mean of the response given by the respondents belonging to Bengaluru Urban is 38.775 and standard deviation is 3.58406. The mean of the response given by the respondents belonging to Chikkaballapur is 32 and standard deviation is 4.75017 for Transactional Leadership among secondary school headmasters working. P value is obtained through multiple comparison and this indicates the following:

- Based on ANOVA, there is a significant difference in the Transactional Leadership of the secondary school headmasters who are working in Rural and Urban districts of Bengaluru Rural since the value of p is less than 0.05.
- There is no significant difference in the Transactional Leadership of the secondary school headmasters who are working in Bengaluru Rural and Chikkaballapur district since the value of p is above 0.05.
- There is a significant difference in the Transactional Leadership of the secondary school headmasters who are working in Bengaluru Urban and Chikkaballapur district since the value of p is less than 0.05.

Hence, this study has indicated that the headmasters who are working in Urban district in Bengaluru have shown greater Transactional Leadership are compared to Chikkaballapur and Bengaluru Rural district. Overall, this study revealed that headmasters who are working in Urban district in Bengaluru was found to be a higher Transactional Leadership as compared to Chikaballapur district and Bengaluru Rural. Difference exists in Transactional Leadership of Bengaluru Urban, Bengaluru Rural district and Chikaballapura district and there is no such difference as mentioned by the teachers working in Chikaballapura district and Bengaluru Rural district.

Graph-3: Comparison of Transactional Leadership dimensions among secondary school headmasters

- H_{04} - There is no significance difference in Laissez-faire Leadership among secondary school headmasters working in Bengaluru Rural, Bengaluru Urban and Chikkaballapur district of Karnataka state.

H₁₄ - There is a significance difference in Laissez-faire Leadership among secondary school headmasters working in Bengaluru Rural, Bengaluru Urban and Chikkaballapur district of Karnataka state.

Table-7: ANOVA - Laissez-faire Leadership among secondary school headmasters

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	S/NS
Between Groups	150.617	2	75.308	26.304	.000	S
Within Groups	334.975	117	2.863			
Total	485.592	119				

Based on the table above, the value of p as indicated below the column titled Sig. is 0.000 and the value of F is 26.304. ANOVA has been applied through SPSS and the table above has been obtained. P value obtained is based on the mean score of Laissez-faire Leadership among secondary school headmasters who are working in rural and urban area of Bengaluru and Chikkaballapur district belonging to Karnataka state. Since the value of p as mentioned in table above is less than 0.05 (based on 5% significant level), based on the value being less than 0.05, the null hypothesis has been rejected and the alternate hypothesis has been accepted. The alternate hypothesis represents difference between Laissez-faire Leadership among secondary school headmasters in rural and urban areas of Bengaluru and Chikkaballapur district of the Karnataka state.

Table-8 : Comparison of differences in Laissez-faire Leadership among secondary school headmasters

Districts	N	Mean	SD	Districts	
				Bengaluru Urban	Chikkaballapur
Bengaluru Rural	40	10.6000	2.12192	.000 (p <.05)	.962 (p > .05)
Bengaluru Urban	40	13.0250	1.22971		.000 (p <.05)
Chikkaballapur	40	10.7000	1.60448		

The above table indicates the number of head masters who have been a part of this study, mean and standard deviation. There are 40 sample of head masters from Rural areas in Bengaluru, 40 from Bengaluru Urban and 40 from Chikkaballapur. The mean of the response given by the respondents belonging to Bengaluru Rural is 10.6 and standard deviation is 2.12192. The mean of the response given by the respondents belonging to Bengaluru Urban is 13.025 and standard deviation is 1.22971. The mean of the response given by the respondents belonging to Chikkaballapur is 10.7 and standard deviation is 1.60448 for Laissez-faire Leadership among secondary school headmasters working. P value is obtained through multiple comparison and this indicates the following:

- Based on ANOVA, there is a significant difference in the Laissez-faire Leadership of the secondary school headmasters who are working in Rural and Urban districts of Bengaluru Rural since the value of p is less than 0.05.
- There is no significant difference in the Laissez-faire Leadership of the secondary school headmasters who are working in Bengaluru Rural and Chikkaballapur district since the value of p is above than 0.05.
- There is a significant difference in the Laissez-faire Leadership of the secondary school headmasters who are working in Bengaluru Urban and Chikkaballapur district since the value of p is less than 0.05.

Hence, this study has indicated that the headmasters who are working in Urban district in Bengaluru have shown greater Laissez-faire Leadership are compared to Chikkaballapur and Bengaluru Rural district. Overall, this study revealed that headmasters who are working in Urban district in Bengaluru was found to be a higher Laissez-faire Leadership as compared to Chikaballapur district and

Bengaluru Rural. Difference exists in Laissez-faire Leadership of Bengaluru Urban, Bengaluru Rural district and Chikaballapura district and there is no such difference as mentioned by the teachers working in Chikaballapura district and Bengaluru Rural district.

Graph-4: Comparison of Laissez-faire Leadership dimensions among secondary school headmasters working in Bengaluru Rural, Bengaluru Urban and Chikkaballapur district of Karnataka state

9. Findings

- Headmasters who are working in Urban district in Bengaluru was found to be a higher leadership style as compared to Chikaballapur district and Bengaluru Rural.
- Difference exists in leadership style and dimension of Bengaluru Urban, Bengaluru Rural district and Chikaballapura district and there is no such difference as mentioned by the teachers working in Chikaballapura district Bengaluru Rural district.
- Headmasters who are working in Urban district in Bengaluru was found to be a higher Transformational leadership as compared to Chikaballapur district and Bengaluru Rural.
- Difference exists in Transformational leadership of Bengaluru Urban, Bengaluru Rural district and Chikaballapura district and there is a difference as mentioned by the teachers working in Chikaballapura district and Bengaluru Rural district.
- Headmasters who are working in Urban district in Bengaluru was found to be a higher Transactional Leadership as compared to Chikaballapur district and Bengaluru Rural.
- Difference exists in Transactional Leadership of Bengaluru Urban, Bengaluru Rural district and Chikaballapura district and there is no such difference as mentioned by the teachers working in Chikaballapura district and Bengaluru Rural district.
- Headmasters who are working in Urban district in Bengaluru was found to be a higher Laissez-faire Leadership as compared to Chikaballapur district and Bengaluru Rural.
- Difference exists in Laissez-faire Leadership of Bengaluru Urban, Bengaluru Rural district and Chikaballapura district and there is no such difference as mentioned by the teachers working in Chikaballapura district and Bengaluru Rural district.

10. Conclusion

Leadership has been explained by internal qualities which are in a person. Thought about traits which differentiated the leaders from their followers can be identified and successful leaders can be identified quickly and are put into leadership positions. Physical, mental and personality characteristics have been examined. The leadership is said to be a line of thought wherein the environmental and situational factors play a very important role in effectiveness level. The Leaders who are leading the organization and the leadership skills which they have play a very important role

and adds towards growth of organization. Leadership can be referred to process of influencing people's behaviour in a way which strives manner that they strive enthusiastically and willingly towards achievement of various group objectives. Overall, this study revealed that headmasters who are working in Urban district in Bengaluru was found to be a higher leadership style as compared to Chikaballapur district and Bengaluru Rural. Difference exists in leadership style and dimension of Bengaluru Urban, Bengaluru Rural district and Chikaballapura district and there is no such difference as mentioned by the teachers working in Chikaballapura district Bengaluru Rural district.

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